

Social Norms, Information Needs and the Experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence among Internally Displaced Women and Girls in Borno State, Nigeria

¹Aderonke KOMOLAFE, ²Prof. Yacob HALISO ³Prof Olajumoke YACOB-HALISO ⁴Dr Obinna OKORO

^{1,2,4}Babcock University, Ogun State, Nigeria

³Brandeis University, Massachusetts, USA

¹aderonkeokeowo@yahoo.com;

²halisoy@babcock.edu.ng

³olaj@brandeis.edu

⁴obinnaokoro44@gmail.com

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Abstract

Purpose of the Study: This paper examines the influence of social norms on the experiences of Sexual Gender Based Violence and information behaviour of internally displaced women and girls in Borno State, Nigeria. This study aims to identify the various needs of female IDPs who have had experiences with SGBV.

Methodology: The study sample was drawn from three local governments: Gwoza, Kondunga, and Monguno in Borno State. A quantitative research approach was adopted in the study. Semi-structured questionnaires were used to collect data from the respondents. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used in data analysis, while the hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Findings: The study revealed that information needs, such as how to access food, shelter, and a source of livelihood, have no significant influence on female internally displaced persons' experience of SGBV. Thus, the presence of these needs does not necessarily increase the expertise of SGBV. However, social norms significantly influence the experience of SGBV among female internally displaced persons.

Recommendations/Conclusion: An increase in socio-cultural beliefs and societal norms such as name-calling, patriarchy, and stigmatisation leads to the rise in the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of female internally displaced persons in Borno State.

Study Type: Empirical study

Keywords: Information Behaviour, Information need, Internally Displaced Persons

Introduction

Conflicts and situations of instability exacerbate pre-existing patterns of discrimination against women and girls, exposing them to heightened risks of violations of their human rights. Armed insurgency in the northeast of Nigeria is perpetuated largely by Boko Haram. This militant Islamist group has killed over 350,000 people, with many more still dying as a result of the indirect effects of the conflict. These indirect effects range from damage to agriculture, water, food, trade and healthcare, spawning one of the worst humanitarian crises in the world today (UNDP, 2020). The United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Types of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW, 1980) upholds women's right to be free from all types of violence and discrimination. This right is a core component of human rights law. According to its understanding, violence against women is a serious kind of discrimination against

women that is illegal under international law, a violation of human rights, and it prevents women from realizing their full potential. In contemporary times, CEDAW has been employed to tackle matters concerning gender-based and sexual violence during conflicts, including safeguarding women from sexual violence associated with such conflicts (Degani, 2018). All acts of violence cause survivors to suffer, be destroyed, or endure misery; as such, gender-based violence violates human rights and keeps survivors from significantly contributing to long-term peace, development, and societal advancement. This is because it is sometimes difficult for victims of violence to freely express who they are or to use the skills they have to make their environment more calming, loving, peaceful, and comfortable (UNICEF, 2014).

Women and girls are disproportionately impacted by armed conflict on a global scale due to their gender and the unequal treatment they receive in society (Bandarage, 2010). Africa has experienced significant occurrences of sexual assault and intimate partner abuse, particularly during times of crisis and global disruptions. This has led to concerns about gender-based violence being referred to as a "shadow pandemic" (UN Women 2020, Yacob-Haliso & Falola, 2021). Since 2009, the Nigerian state has been afflicted by insurgency and acts of terrorism perpetrated by the Islamic extremist group known as Boko Haram (Njoku and Akintayo, 2021). As a result, almost 1.8 million Nigerians have been forced to leave their homes in the northern region of the country (Nwoga et al., 2018). By the end of 2020, Nigeria had a total of 2.9 million internally displaced persons (IDPs). Among them, 79% were women and children who were forced to flee their homes due to the fighting between the government and the Boko Haram Movement. This conflict has resulted in an increase in gender-based violence (Ajayi, 2020; IDMC, 2020). According to a study by the IOM, there were a total of 2,197,824 Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) recognised in 452,219 households as of 2022, a figure that has not shown any signs of reducing, with many deaths and displacement of people, with high occurrences of human rights violations ongoing around many parts of the country (Kotso et al., 2023). The Beijing statement, issued during the Fourth World Congress on Women, affirms that while armed conflicts impact all segments of society, women and girls are disproportionately affected due to their societal status and gender (Yacob-Haliso, 2012). During times of armed conflict, sexual abuse, which encompasses crimes such as rape, forced oral sex, mutilation of sexual organs, forced pregnancy, and prostitution, is employed as a means to forward the objectives of the battlefield (Wilbers, 1994). UN Women (2023), states that women and girls bear the brunt of armed conflict due to their disadvantaged position in society and their gender. Sexual gender-based violence in Africa is primarily attributed to cultural factors stemming from a patriarchal socio-cultural framework. Sex/age hierarchies that are inflexible establish men in a position of superiority over women and girls. Gender norms uphold this arrangement and thus diminish the worth of women and girls. Additionally, violence is employed to reinforce these norms, subjugating the feminine gender and justifying different types of violence. Afro-cultural apologists argue that the perceived injustices against women in Africa are deeply ingrained in African culture. Olayanju et al. (2013) argue that African social morality inherently promotes the subjection of women and that these inequalities are seen to be advantageous for women. Sociocultural norms are commonly identified as a significant element contributing to sexual gender-based violence against women and girls (Benebo et al., 2018). Socio-cultural norms prevalent in regions such as Nigeria, particularly in the Northern areas, hinder abused women from reporting incidents of gender-based violence (GBV). In Kenya, it is estimated that a woman experiences sexual violation every thirty minutes. However, due to stigma, fear of retaliation, and lack of knowledge about the law and one's rights, many women choose to remain silent, feeling trapped and helpless, and often endure their suffering in secret (Njogu & McHardy, 2009). Culture, tradition, and religion play a pivotal role in inciting gender-based violence, which in turn inflicts harm upon women's reproductive health, overall well-being, and their ability to actively engage in the economy and society. Research has shown that individuals who have experienced sexual violence

actively seek out ways to adapt and cope when they experience physical symptoms that require medical treatment (WHO, 2021).

Information behaviour can be defined as the study of how individuals need, seek, and utilise information in various situations in their daily lives to accomplish specific goals or objectives (Soroya et al., 2021). It is the overall manner in which individuals engage with sources and channels of information. This can involve both active and passive information seeking, such as face-to-face communication and the passive reception of information (Bharadwaj & Khan, 2016). An example of this can be seen in the case of female internally displaced persons who may actively or passively engage with sources of help and assistance. (Pettigrew et al., 2001; Wilson, 2000).

Wilson (1997) developed a model for information behaviour which suggests three elements as components of information behaviour that can be adapted in the context of IDPs and SGBV: information needs and its drives, i.e. the factors that give rise to an individual's perception of need such as the circumstance of displacement, sexual violence and the need for survival, factors that affect the individual's response to the perception of needs in terms of social and cultural factors as well as processes or actions involved in that response in the choice of disclosure or non-disclosure and help-seeking behaviour.

In actual fact, the information need is based on an existing initially identified need for which the information is actually sought. These needs are basic physiological needs like safety, shelter, and the need to survive and be free from all forms of sexual gender-based violence (Adejumo et al., 2022; Perrin et al., 2019). These factors influence how individuals respond to their identified information needs, including socio-cultural factors that shape their responses.

Statement of the Problem

Borno State currently accommodates a total of 874,213 internally displaced persons in 62 formal and 158 informal camps spread throughout 17 Local Government Areas. The occurrence of displacement, often caused by armed conflict, has led to the continuation of various forms of Sexual Gender-Based Violence, such as rape, sexual abuse, sexual harassment and intimate partner violence. Women and girls make up more than 50% of the population of IDPs in camps living below US \$1. Consequently, many find themselves at risk of sexual and gender-based violence in the camps as a result of overlapping vulnerabilities associated with economic security and protection. Women and girls in the camps reported significant challenges such as difficulty in getting firewood, irregular food and water supply, and poor shelters – as major factors fueling sexual exploitation in the camps. Female IDPs, particularly unmarried women under the age of 20, are frequently sexually exploited when on their way to collect firewood or water, asking for money on the streets, or spending nights on the streets due to poor shelters in camps. According to the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs, Nigeria recorded 27,693 cases of Sexual Gender-Based Violence between 2020 to 2023.

Socio-cultural factors deeply embedded in the social structure of communities and society have a significant impact on shaping attitudes, behaviours, and norms regarding gender roles, power dynamics, and interpersonal relationships. As a result, they have been identified as the primary causes of gender-based violence that significantly contribute to the occurrence of sexual gender-based violence (SGBV). Gender-based violence stems from patriarchal attitudes that perpetuate male control over females. These are societal behaviours that perpetuate male dominance over women, such as paying a bridal price or assigning gender roles to men and women. This mindset causes women to remain subservient and obedient even when they are physically, sexually, or emotionally abused. Patriarchy maintains the belief that the female gender is inferior due to the process of sex role socialization, which promotes male dominance and is supported by various religions and cultures that assign women a disadvantaged and submissive position. In patriarchal civilisations such as Africa and Nigeria, there is widespread acceptance of SGBV (Sexual and Gender-Based Violence) as a societal norm. This acceptance further

worsens the continuation and occurrence of sexual violence. In Nigeria and Africa, cultural norms and traditions indicate that when a dowry is paid for a woman, she is considered the husband's property. As a result, he has the freedom to treat her as he wishes without facing any consequences (Aluko, 2015). Spousal rape is not considered a crime in many cultures, which leads to high rates of intimate partner violence. Women often hesitate to report this form of sexual violence due to fear of retaliation and abandonment by their partners (Ajayi et al., 2021; Awosusi & Ogundana, 2015; Horne et al., 2013). Information is fundamental to human existence; it is a critical resource for the development and advancement of any society or people. Internally displaced persons have a basic need for information on how to get food, shelter, potable water, healthcare, education, security and clothing. Persons facing the challenges of displacement as a result of armed conflicts need information that will enable them to manage stress, combat anxiety, put an end to their current experience, survive and lead a better life, or cope with their current realities (George & Adelaja, 2022). Accessing and effectively using the right information will empower women and girls living in IDP camps by equipping them with the ability to make informed choices, create effective and long-lasting strategies for survival, and actively pursue solutions to combat further experiences of sexual violence while also safeguarding them against manipulation and additional abuse (Eweka & Olusegun, 2016; Pikirayi & Bamidele, 2022).

Hypothesis

H₁: Socio norms have no significant influence on the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of female Internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria.

H₂: Information need has no significant influence on the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of female Internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria.

Literature Review

The shared experiences and interactions of individual persons in a community, informal rules that dictate how a person should behave influence behaviour and form the basis for the community's social reality constructed by the culture, norms, values, traditions and beliefs held by the people (Hamilton & Marsh 2016). Many times, the construction of these social realities among a group of people is largely informal, taking place during conversations, interactions, and discussions about experiences and events of common interest. The actions, inactions and behaviour of people are generally determined by human nature and culture, predetermined by socially acceptable roles and personality. The behaviour of an individual can be said to be a product of prescribed social roles based on culture. Social roles are made up of normative beliefs and actions that result from culturally derived psychological interpretations of social settings (Eagly & Wood, 2016).

Culture is the set of behaviours that develop out of a fundamental understanding held by members of a group of people and channelled towards addressing issues arising from the larger ecological setting where the group exists in order to satisfy biological and social needs and motives (Caperon et al., 2022). It embodies shared meanings and social behaviours that are passed on from one generation to another, which allows a community of people to meet their needs, pursue socially acceptable communal goals and make meaning from life. Cultural worldviews, ideologies, and practices are the lenses through which groups of people are able to interpret and understand the world. It influences social behaviours (Matsumoto, 2006). Cultures, traditions as well and religions the world over have for centuries determined and influenced the behaviours and interactions between male and female social roles and, as such, entrenched male dominance into the way society is organized and the way society functions, thereby fostering the idea of gender inequality (Udoh et al., 2020).

Research Methodology

The study adopted a quantitative research method. Quantitative data was collected through a semi-structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The semi-structured nature of the questionnaire allowed for open-ended questions that elucidated rich responses due to the nature of SGBV. Simple random sampling was used in selecting the number of respondents for the quantitative study from each of the 3 local governments to represent the internally displaced persons camps in Borno state. Using a simple random sampling method ensured that each unit in the sample had an equal probability of being selected. This technique provides an accurate and unbiased estimation of the parameters of a homogeneous population (Singh & Masuku, 2014). Therefore, the semi-structured questionnaire was administered to 250 participants from the general population of 667 women drawn from Konduga, Gwoza and Monguno Local government areas in Borno State.

Sample size distribution

LOCATIONS	CASES	SAMPLES
Gwoza	400	150
Monguno	200	75
Konduga	67	25
Total	667	250

Frequency counts, percentages, mean, and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while simple and multiple linear regression analyses were used to test the hypotheses postulated in the study.

Results

Hypothesis one: Socio-norms have no significant influence on the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of female internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria.

Table 1

Influence of Socio-Norms on the Experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of Female Internally Displaced Persons

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t	p	R ²
(Constant)	9.509	1.963		4.844	.000	0.44
Socio Norms	1.597	.114	.663	13.944	.000	

Dependent Variable: Experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence

Source: Field Survey 2024, *Note:* β = Standardized Coefficient, significant at 0.05

Table 1. The table shows that socio-norms had a positive significant influence on the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of female internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria ($R^2 = 0.439$, $\beta = 0.663$, $t(248) = 13944$, $p < 0.05$). This suggests that socio-norms significantly predict the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence by female internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected. The analysis shows that socio-norms could explain 44% ($R^2 = 0.44$) variation in the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of female internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria. This analysis implies that an increase in the application of socio-norms by female internally displaced persons in Borno State would lead to intensification in the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence among the female internally displaced persons. For instance, Baird et al. (2019) found that in East African IDP camps, socio-cultural norms often restricted women's movements and social interactions, limiting their exposure to

information about protective measures or reporting options for SGBV. Socio-norms, such as patriarchal structures and community stigmas around discussing SGBV, shape how women interpret and use the information they receive. Similarly, Chynoweth (2018) found out that even when women in displaced settings access resources or information on SGBV, they may hesitate to act on this knowledge due to fear of social repercussions or cultural stigma, reducing the effectiveness of these resources. Thus, socio-norms are known predictors of the experience of SGBV among female IDPs in Borno State.

Hypothesis two: Information need has no significant influence on the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of female internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria.

Table 2

Influence of Information Need on Experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence by Female Internally Displaced Persons

Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t	p	R ²
(Constant)	37.293	3.400		10.968	.000	0.001
Information Need	-.052	.147	-.023	-.357	.721	

Dependent Variable: Sexual Gender-Based Violence

The table shows that information need had no significant influence on the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of female internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria ($R^2 = 0.001$, $\beta = -0.023$, $t(248) = -0.357$, $p > 0.05$). This suggests that the information needs of female internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria, do not influence their experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence. Consequently, the null hypothesis was accepted. The analysis shows that the information need could explain less than 1% ($R^2 = 0.001$) variation in the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of female internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria. This analysis implies that information need on its own does not predict the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence among female internally displaced persons in Borno State, Nigeria.

The study revealed female IDPs needed information on how to get food to feed their families, security and protection, how to go to school and get educated, how to get good or better accommodation and how to access healthcare. Furthermore, the female internally displaced persons who had experienced Sexual Gender-Based Violence in Borno State, Nigeria, also required important information on the source of livelihood and how to make a living to care for their families and to be aware of current happenings. Even though their needs were very important, as revealed in the analysis of the different types of needs, they had, information need recorded no significant influence on female IDPs' experience of SGBV in Borno State. the implication of this is that in spite of the enormous needs that female IDPs have, the existence of these needs does not necessarily increase their experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Internally displaced women and girls often have significant unmet needs for information relating to survival, protection, and coping strategies. Accessing information on healthcare, food security, legal protection, SGBV services such as counselling and safe spaces is vital for the women and girls, as they face heightened vulnerability in displacement contexts. An increase in socio-cultural beliefs and societal norms leads to an increase in the experience of Sexual Gender-Based Violence of female internally displaced persons in Borno State. Traditional gender expectations often isolate victims, affecting their willingness to seek support. These socio-cultural dynamics increase the vulnerability of displaced women to repeated abuse and hinder effective interventions for addressing SGBV. social and cultural beliefs are particularly responsible for the high rate of experience of SGBV among displaced persons

in conflict-affected communities. Blaming, stigmatisation and victimization are some of the problems sponsored by socio-cultural factors faced by female IDPs.

For improved service delivery in the eradication of SGBV programs, government and humanitarian aid agencies should prioritize background in-depth population and community analysis. This will help to understudy the people and learn about their peculiar nature, which could be different from those of similar cultures; generalisations should not be made. It is also important that government and implementing non-government organisations should constantly conduct surveys, monitoring and evaluation activities focused on the women and girls in these affected communities. This will help to know first-hand what their current and actual information needs are and not to deal with perceived needs that may be suggestions or impressions of intermediaries such as community leaders.

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